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ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT: INPUTS TO
A PROPOSED INTERVENTION PROGRAM**

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Teacher Education Administrators' Emotional Quotient and its Relation to their Leadership Style and Organizational Commitment: Inputs to a Proposed Intervention Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the emotional quotient of teacher education administrators' and its relation to leadership style and organizational commitment in the college of Education of selected State Universities and colleges in the National Capital Region during the first semester of school year 2016-2017 which could be used as inputs for developing a proposed intervention program. The descriptive method of research was used in this study with the questionnaire and documentary analysis as data gathering instruments. It was found out that among the school administrators from the selected State colleges and universities respondents, the level of emotional quotient of teacher education administrators from SUC 2 in terms of trustful marked as high degree and generally timid, gregarious and bias to an above average it implies that the though administrator in this school manifested timidity and being biased, it can be clinched that administrators from this SUC also exhibited sociable individuals. These characteristics can motivate the faculty to do their task with a merry heart. Also, both respondents perceived almost the same level on the transformational leadership style for all the dimensions. It is in the indicator C- Work management only had a verbal interpretation of high extent and perceived by the administrators. An indication of trust bestowed by the superior to their subordinates. Furthermore, the school administrators in the Selected SUCs are practicing the transactional leadership style in all the five dimensions. There is a slight opposition in using the same especially in dimension D- Problem Solving. It was perceived by the school administrators and in Human Resource Development which was perceived by the faculty.

Keywords: *emotional quotient, leadership style, organizational commitment, SUC*

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a significant change in the responsibilities and demands of administrators. The emergent global nature of the world, servant expectations of the society, and increased demand of accountability for student achievement, has necessitated administrators to improve their leadership abilities. No longer do administrators serve only as facilities and process managers of a school; they need other skills. To be successful leaders of a school today, in the light of public demands, and to ensure all students achieve academic success, administrators must have a broad focus and understanding. If success is to occur and be sustained, it is the skill for leading people which will make the ultimate difference (Bipath and Fullan, 2014).

School administrators must comprehend, appreciate and manage the emotional nature of those affiliated with the school at all levels to create an environment which fosters high expectations and motivation toward meeting those expectations. To accomplish this, school leaders need to possess and demonstrate high skill in an area that has gained abundant attention in business leadership, and in recent years, an increasing amount in school leadership research emotional intelligence (Curry, et al., 2014).

Greenockle (2014) asserts that School leaders who possess emotional intelligence will understand the important role their emotional management plays in shaping the school's culture. By being a leader who is calm in times of trial, bases decisions on fact without emotional interference, yet, with empathy directed to solutions, School Administrators build trust, respect, and motivation within the school community.

In this regard, school administrators' emotional intelligence, leadership abilities and organizational commitment may significantly impact the learning environment of a school. Lahey (2013) argued that it does not necessarily make a difference what school administrators do. It is how they perform their responsibilities that matters. The manner they complete their responsibilities, interact, read, and respond to others can determine their success as a leader and organizational commitment.

Today, schools require a leadership that is able to meet vast demands and orchestrate a place where teachers teach to higher levels and students achieve to their maximum potential. For this to occur, the school leader needs not only be intelligent, possess instructional knowledge, and understand local, state, and federal guidelines, policies, and law, they also need to know why, when, and how to act. The changed role of school administrators from a manager to an instructional leader with the ability to provide syntheses of responsibilities, has focused research on what the School Administrators can actually do to positively impact student achievement.

Emotional intelligence, leadership style and organizational commitment have been studied from many angles over the years; yet, there is still uncertainty about what it takes to effectively lead an organization, what is the effect of level of emotional quotient and how the leaders' organizational commitment upshot toward success in the lives and performance of school teachers and students. Many of these studies indicate that a leader must have the ability to develop, inspire, motivate, and effectively communicate the organization's vision to move people toward successfully meeting the vision, which is as considered one measure of success (Greenockle, et al, 2013).

Relatively, in this changing environment, leadership is seen by many synonymous with the success of the organization. Nowadays leaders must be more adaptable in this context of continuous change and uncertainty. Future leaders will have to adapt their leadership style depending on the context, ensuring that results are obtained. Qualities such as self-awareness, empathy, confidence and emotional intelligence will come forward. Additionally, to struggle with continuous change, personalities and behavior will determine how successful leaders will be, but as expectations rise, the future leaders will have to earn the right to lead others.

Thus, a leader must take into consideration his personal strengths and style in each of these five areas to understand their levels of emotional quotient and the others. A good question is why emotional quotient is needed in leadership. Analyzing theory, we concluded that the emotional quotient of leaders can be best observed at the work place as that is the context where its effects may be noticed.

From the foregoing views and observations of various authorities and organizations, the researcher was influenced and motivated to conduct this research study on emotional intelligence and its relationship to leadership style and organizational commitment of administrators in selected state universities and colleges in the national capital region.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the emotional quotient of teacher education administrators' and its relation to leadership style and organizational commitment in the college of Education of selected State Universities and Colleges in the National Capital Region during the first semester of school year 2016-17 which could be used as inputs for developing a proposed intervention program. More specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of emotional quotient of teacher education administrators as shown by the results of the Standardized Emotional Quotient (SEQ Test)?
2. What is the leadership style of the teacher education administrator respondents in terms of the following dimensions?
 - 2.1. transformational; and
 - 2.2. transactional?
3. Are there significant differences in the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the leadership style of the teacher education administrators in terms of the given dimensions?
4. What is the level of organizational commitment of the teacher education administrators in terms of the following dimensions as perceived by the faculty and the administrator respondents?
 - 4.1. affective;
 - 4.2. continuance; and
 - 4.3. normative?
5. Is there a significant difference in the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the level of commitment of the teacher education administrators in terms of the three given dimensions?
6. Are there significant relationships between the teacher education administrators' emotional quotient and the following variables?
 - 6.1. leadership style; and
 - 6.2. organizational commitment?

Literature Review

For more than a decade, the concept of emotional quotient has attained wide attention as a potentially productive factor in describing and forecasting one's job performance. This umbrella concept capitulates a wide array of individual predisposition and performance, conceived as soft, intrapersonal and interpersonal skills which exist outside the conventional scenario of parochial knowledge, general intelligence, organizational and technical skills (Kierstead, 2014).

In this connection, Gray (2013) asserted that emotional quotient is the cornerstone of every decision an administrator makes; solving problems and making judgments are a part of a leader's system of values and beliefs. A school administrators' emotional quotient and management skills are vital to a collaborative effort to increase student achievement and to ensure the school's well-being as a learning community.

Likewise, Fullan (2013) implied that school administrator who are emotionally intelligent are aware of their own emotional composition and are sensitive and inspiring to others. He also stated that school administrator who has good status of emotional quotient are able to handle daily school related problems and think conceptually as they transform the school organization through teachers and community organizations. School administrator with the capacity to successfully express their fundamental feelings and emotions are crucial to effective school leadership.

Relatively, Goleman, et al. (2014) have explored the strength of this relationship by considering the characteristics of leaders. Based on the traits that leaders share, they are considered to be people who look to the horizon and strive to change the current paradigm, from different perspectives than those considered by their followers. They are visionary people who are considered "Quality leaders" because they seek to achieve total quality in the organization, starting with their own personalities and traits.

Moreover, according to Ruderman, et. al. (2013), highly emotionally intelligent leaders are successful leaders; they hold the necessary skills of emotional intelligence and control of their competencies associated with leadership performance that drives improved results.

Meanwhile, Fry (2013), explains leadership as use of leading strategy to offer inspiring motive and to enhance the staff's potential for growth and development. Leadership can be broadly defined as the relationship between an individual and a group built around some common interest wherein the group behaves in a manner directed or determined by the leader. The leader thus becomes the interpreter of the interests and objectives of the group, as the group in turn recognizes and accepts the interpreter as its spokesperson.

Several reasons indicate that there should be a relationship between leadership style and organizational performance. The first is that today's intensive and dynamic markets feature innovation-based competition, price/performance rivalry, decreasing returns, and the creative destruction of existing competencies Santora et al. (2013).

Studies have suggested that effective leadership behaviors can facilitate the improvement of performance when organizations face these new challenges. McGrath (2013) stated that understanding the effects of leadership on performance is also important because leadership is viewed by some researchers as one of the key driving forces for improving a firm's performance. Effective leadership is seen as a potent source of management development and sustained competitive advantage for organizational performance improvement Avolio et al. (2013). A study conducted by Smith (2015) entitled Leadership Skills and Emotional Intelligence; Determinant factors for job commitment and satisfaction revealed that, emotionally intelligent leaders are associated with better performance in the following areas: participative management, putting people at ease, self – awareness, balance between personal life and work, straight forwardness and composure, building and mending relationships, doing what it takes, decisiveness confronting problem employees and change management.

Another relevant study was conducted by David (2014) with a title, “The Effects of School Leaders’ Emotional Intelligence, School System and Organizational Value Orientation in Teachers’ Organizational Commitment and Job satisfaction” which sought to determine whether emotional intelligence of school leaders, school systems and organizational value orientation affects the teachers’ organizational commitment and job satisfaction. The findings revealed that the normative value of orientation and leaders’ emotional intelligence was associated with diminished job satisfaction.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive method of research. According to Shields, Patricia and Rangarjan (2014) descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. It does not answer questions about how/when /why the characteristics occurred. Rather it addresses the “what” question (what are the characteristics of the population or situation being studied?) It is also the best methods for collecting information that will demonstrate relationships and describe the world as it exists. As such, the researcher perceived this as the most appropriate method for this study.

Respondents

The sources of data of the study were the 20 Administrators and 120 faculty members in the four selected state universities of National Capital Region namely: Polytechnic University of the Philippines, Marikina Polytechnic College, Eulogio Amang Rodriguez Institute of Science and Technology and Technological University of the Philippines.

Instrument

The data gathering instrument used in this study was three survey questionnaires. The first questionnaire contains eight indicators to determine the emotional quotient of the school administrators in four State Colleges and Universities. It is a standardized test. Hence, no validation of expert needed. The second and third were self-generated questionnaires which was checked by her adviser. The designed questionnaire was then validated by a group of experts.

Procedure

A letter of request address to the school head and to the respondents was first prepared seeking their approval to conduct the study. The cooperative procedure and effort in retrieving the accomplished questionnaires through the help of the head of the agency, secretaries and some researcher's friends in the respective schools had also been requested.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Level of Emotional Quotient of Teacher Education Administrators as Shown by the Results of the Standardized Emotional Quotient (SEQ Test)

Table 1 presents the extent of emotional Quotient of Teacher Education Administrator-Respondents from four State Universities and Colleges. In consideration of the level where the highest frequencies occur, the administrators are described above average and mid-

average trustful but below-average distrustful. This is an indication that the administrators are more trustful than distrustful to at least mid- average level. In the same vein, the administrators can be described dyscontrolled, with mid- average rating, than controlled rated as very low.

Table 1. *Emotions Profile Index of SUC 1-4*

		Very Superior	Superior	Above Ave.	High Ave.	Mid Ave.	Low Ave.	Below Ave.	Low	Very Low	Remarks
		97-above	90-96	75-89	60-74	40-59	25-39	24-10	4-9	3-0	
1.	Trustful	1	4	5	2	4	1	2		1	Above Average -Mid Average
2.	Dyscontrolled		1	3		9	3	1	3		Mid Average
3.	Timid	2	3	2	4	3	2	3	1		High Average -Mid Average
4.	Depressed	1	5	3	2	7	1	1			Mid Average
5.	Distrustful		1		3		2	7	2	5	Below Average
6.	Controlled		1	4	1	4	3	2	1	4	Very Low
7.	Aggressive		1	2	4	3	5	5			Low Average -Below Average
8.	Gregarious			5	2	4	7		1	1	Above Average -Low Average
9.	Bias		2	6	6		1	2	3		Above Average -High Average

Moreover, they are more timid, with mid to high average rating, than aggressive, with low to below average rating. These administrators are expected to be outspoken and can verbalize what he wants and what he feels to be a certain extent.

The group of administrators is seemingly a mixture of depressed and gregarious individuals. There are more depressed ones to a mid-average level but a larger number were found to be a gregarious to a high, mid and low average level. Most of them tend to show bias to a high average level. They have bias to an above to high average level.

Leadership Style of the Teacher Education Administrator Respondents

Table 2. *Respondents' Perceptions on Transformational Leadership in Terms of Formulation of Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO)*

	Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
		WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1.	encourages the faculty and the student respondents in the formulation of the Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO) of the College.	4.20	0.95	HE	4.09	0.86	HE
2.	encourages the faculty and the students to use their creativity and innovative ideas in the formulation of the VMGO.	4.20	1.06	HE	4.08	0.90	HE
3.	emphasizes the significance of having a collective sense of mission.	4.35	0.67	HE	4.07	0.86	HE
Overall Weighted Mean		4.25		HE	4.08		HE
Standard deviation		0.79			0.81		

Formulation of vision, mission, goals and objectives of the institution is one of the five aspects of transformational leadership of the administrators. In this regard, the administrators perceived that they have manifested these to a high extent as indicated by weighted means ranging from 4.20 to 4.35. The faculty perceived the administrators to have exhibited these equally well to a high extent, with weighted means ranging from 4.07 to 4.09, relatively lower than those of the administrators. The responses reflect the fact that both groups of respondents, administrators and faculty, perceived that the administrators encourage the faculty and students to use their creativity and innovative ideas and participate in the formulation of the school's mission, vision, goals and objectives. In this way, the participants will realize the significance of having a collective sense of mission. In eliciting the involvement of the school's constituents in the formulation of the VMGO, there is a greater likelihood that they will have the responsibility and the willingness to implement them to the best of their capability. Such involvement could bring about transformation in the institution.

Table 3. *Respondents' Perceptions on Transformational Leadership in Terms of Policy Implementation*

	Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
		WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1.	Demonstrates proper behavior in consonance with the implementation of college policies.	4.55	0.51	VHE	4.14	0.82	HE
2.	Demonstrates enthusiasm and optimism in implementing policies.	4.53	0.51	VHE	4.07	0.88	HE
3.	Encourages the faculty and students to work closely in implementing college policies.	4.45	0.83	HE	4.01	0.92	HE
Overall Weighted Mean		4.49		HE	4.07		HE
Standard deviation		0.52			0.81		

In terms of policy implementation, the administrators were perceived to have demonstrated proper behavior and enthusiasm optimism to a very high extent as indicated by weighted means of 4.55 and 4.53. However, encouraging the faculty and students to work closely in implementing college policies has been perceived to have been demonstrated only to a high extent, with weighted mean of 4.45.

On the other hand, the faculty opined that the three indicators have been manifested to a high extent, as indicated by weighted means ranging from 4.01 to 4.14. Although the overall results tend to show that the administrators were perceived to manifest transformational leadership to a high extent, the numerical values showed a higher level of perception of the administrators (4.49) than that of the faculty (4.07), which could imply lesser optimism and enthusiasm and proper behavior among administrators.

The relatively greater standard deviation in the responses of the faculty tend to show a wider range of perceptions than those of the administrators.

Table 4. Respondents' Perceptions on Transformational Leadership in Terms of Work Management

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. emphasizes commitment towards the accomplishment of tasks.	4.75	0.55	VHE	4.22	0.71	HE
2. provides support to the faculty in the accomplishment of their work.	4.70	0.47	VHE	3.95	0.90	HE
3. practices empowerment of the faculty in the management of their work.	4.60	0.60	VHE	3.95	0.89	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	4.68		VHE	4.04		HE
Standard deviation	0.46			0.74		

With regard to work management as dimension of transformational leadership, the administrators perceived themselves to have emphasized commitment to work, provided support and empowered the faculty in this aspect to a very high extent, with weighted means of 4.75, 4.70 and 4.60, respectively. However, in all these three indicators the faculty perceived that the administrators have manifested these indicators to a high extent, with lower weighted means ranging from 3.95 to 4.22.

It is obvious in the overall results wherein the perceptions of the administrators are higher than those of the faculty, both in weighted mean and in the verbal interpretation.

Apparently, the faculty did not perceive the transformational leadership of the administrators in terms of work management in the same level as the perception of the administrators particularly in terms of support and empowerment.

Table 5. Respondents' Perceptions on Transformational Leadership in Terms of Problem Solving

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. encourages the faculty to approach problems in new ways.	4.55	0.60	VHE	3.94	0.97	HE
2. re-examines critical assumptions to determine whether they are appropriate.	4.55	0.51	VHE	4.00	0.89	HE
3. motivates and stimulate his/her followers to solve their problems.	4.30	0.98	HE	3.93	0.90	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	4.47		HE	3.96		HE
Standard deviation	0.58			0.86		

Transformational leadership in terms of problem solving involves finding new approaches, examining the appropriateness of critical assumptions and motivating and stimulating the followers in solving their problems. In this regard, the administrators felt that they have done the first two to a very high extent, and the third to a high extent.

In the perception of the faculty, unlike the administrators all the indicators were perceived by the faculty to a high extent. Although the overall means resulted to the same level of high extent, the numerical results point to a higher level of perception of the administrators than that the faculty. This could imply that the faculty expects more than what the administrators have shown.

Table 6. Respondents' Perceptions on Transformational Leadership in Terms of Human Resources Development

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. invests in the development of the faculty.	4.50	0.61	VHE	3.82	1.10	HE
2. provides learning opportunities for the development of the faculty and the students.	4.45	0.69	HE	3.85	1.07	HE
3. takes into account the individual needs of the faculty and the desires within a group.	4.40	0.60	HE	3.76	1.14	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	4.45		HE	3.81		HE
Standard deviation	0.52			1.04		

Human resource development is primarily focus on development of faculty and students in terms of skills and strategies. For this, there should be an assessment of what these groups need and desire. In this regard, and providing the opportunities for learning, both administrators and faculty perceived them to have been done to a high extent. Such measures entail budgetary allocation. According to the administrators, they have made investments to a very high extent. But the faculty felt that this has been done to a high extent only.

Investments could be in terms of sending the faculty to seminars and conferences, giving study grants, providing funds for research, and other benefits. There is a possibility that not everybody has been given equal opportunities that brought about a lower level of perception of the faculty on this indicator numerically. The verbal interpretation, however, resulted to the same level of high extent.

Table 7. Respondents' Perceptions on Transactional Leadership in Terms of Formulation of Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO)

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. instructs the faculty to join the preparation of the VMGO of the College.	3.55	1.28	HE	3.97	0.82	HE
2. involves those faculty and students who are self-motivated.	3.70	1.34	HE	3.89	0.89	HE
3. guides the faculty on how to perform their tasks.	3.90	1.25	HE	3.88	0.91	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.72		HE	3.91		HE
Standard deviation	1.17			0.81		

The five dimensions reflected in transformational leadership are again considered, but this time, in terms of transactional leadership. As regards the formulation of vision, mission goals and objectives, giving instructions and guides the faculty in the performance of their tasks were perceived by the administrators and faculty as having been manifested to a high extent, similarly in involving self-motivated faculty and students. The weighted means in these three indicators for the two groups of respondents are close to each other. It will be noted, however, that the standard deviations in the responses of the administrators are greater than their counterparts in the responses of the faculty. This could imply that the strategies of the administrators in these dimensions could vary in consideration of the situations and conditions particular in their respective schools.

The overall means are 3.72 and 3.91 for the administrators and faculty, respectively, indicating an overall verbal interpretation of having manifested the indicators to a high extent.

Table 8. Respondents' Perceptions on Transactional Leadership in Terms of Policy Implementation

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. monitors actively the implementation of college policies.	4.05	0.94	HE	3.89	0.82	HE
2. takes corrective actions to prevent mistakes in the policy implementation.	3.95	1.00	HE	3.94	0.84	HE
3. tells his/her subordinates to follow strictly the college policies.	4.05	1.18	HE	3.95	0.78	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	4.02		HE	3.93		HE
Standard deviation	0.97			0.75		

Policy implementation in transactional leadership primarily involves monitoring, taking corrective actions and making sure that the subordinates strictly follow the school's policies. To this end, both administrators and faculty perceived the administrators to have done these to a high extent, in consideration of the weighted means, which do not vary so much from each other.

With overall weighted means of 4.02 and 3.93, and standard deviations of 0.97 and 0.75, apparently, there is congruence in what the administrators and faculty perceived on what the administrators manifested.

Table 9. Respondents' Perceptions on Transactional Leadership in Terms of Work Management

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. expresses satisfaction when the faculty meet expectations.	3.95	1.32	HE	3.90	0.93	HE
2. gives rewards to those who do their work well.	3.75	1.33	HE	3.65	1.03	HE
3. actively monitors the work of the faculty.	3.95	1.23	HE	3.85	0.89	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.88		HE	3.80		HE
Standard deviation	1.27			0.85		

To achieve transactional leadership in terms of work management, it is desired that the administrator actively monitors the work of the faculty, expresses satisfaction for work done as expected and gives rewards for work well done. Those have been done by the administrators to a high extent. The faculty expresses similar perceptions about their administrators, as indicated by overall means of 3.88 and 3.80. A greater standard deviation for administrator could mean a wider variation in their responses.

Table 10. Respondents' Perceptions on Transactional Leadership in Terms of Problem Solving

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. resolves problem as they arise.	4.05	1.19	HE	3.90	0.86	HE
2. interferes in the faculty's problem when they become serious.	3.35	1.35	ME	3.81	0.94	HE
3. relies on standard forms of punishment and sanction to control followers.	3.58	1.17	HE	3.78	0.95	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.67		HE	3.83		HE
Standard deviation	1.11			0.82		

It can be observed that the administrators did not indicate any response about interfering in the faculty’s problems. But as indicated by the responses of the faculty, it may be interfered that the administrators have done this to a high extent. On resolving problems as they arise and giving standard form of punishment, both groups of respondents perceived these to have been exhibited to a high extent.

It may be interfered that administrators are also concerned with the problems of the faculty and will not let these go unresolved. Problems of the teachers could affect their teaching performance and administrator are most likely aware of this.

Table 11. Respondents’ Perceptions on Transactional Leadership in Terms of Human Resources Development

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. provides scholarship to those who are performers.	3.35	1.14	ME	3.53	1.14	HE
2. conducts training programs for the faculty.	3.85	1.18	HE	3.74	1.00	HE
3. shows the power to reinforce the subordinates for their successful development.	3.90	1.21	HE	3.75	1.01	HE
Overall Weighted Mean		3.70	HE	3.67	HE	
Standard deviation		1.07		0.95		

The measures toward human resource development are actual steps such as providing scholarship, conducting training programs and ensuring successful development. The administrators did not express their perception on the providing scholarship probably it is because no faculty pass the criteria for scholarship grant set by the management.

But the faculty mentioned that this has been done to a high extent. The other two items were perceived to have been done to a high extent for both groups of respondents. Both the overall means and standard deviations have close values for the two groups.

Significant Differences in the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Leadership Style of the Teacher Education Administrators

Table 12. Summary of Test of Difference between the Respondents’ Perceptions on Transformational Leadership Style Using t-Test

Dimensions	Computed t Value	Critical t Values	Decision	Interpretation
A. Formulation of Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO)	0.90	±2.093	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
B. Policy Implementation	2.06	±2.093	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
C. Work Management	5.16	±2.093	Reject the Ho	Significant
D. Problem Solving	3.36	±2.093	Reject the Ho	Significant
E. Human Resources Development	4.21	±2.093	Reject the Ho	Significant

As presented in the table, the computed t values of formulation of Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO) (0.90), and policy implementation (2.06) are within the critical t values of -2.093 and 2.093, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. It concludes that there is no significant difference between the respondents’ perceptions of transformational leadership in terms of formulation of Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO), and policy implementation.

While the computed t values of work management (5.16), problem solving (3.36) and human resources development (4.21) are higher than the critical t value of 2.093, this means that the perceptions of respondents on transformational leadership in terms of work management, problem solving, and human resources development differ significantly. The level of perceptions of the administrators are higher than those of the faculty.

Table 13. Summary of Test of Difference between the Respondents’ Perceptions on Transactional Leadership Using t-Test

Dimensions	Computed t Value	Critical t Values	Decision	Interpretation
A. Formulation of Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO)	-0.71	±2.093	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
B. Policy Implementation	0.40	±2.093	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
C. Work Management	0.29	±2.093	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
D. Problem Solving	-0.63	±2.093	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
E. Human Resources Development	0.11	±2.093	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant

As revealed in Table 30, the computed t values of all transactional leadership dimensions are between the critical t values of -2.093 and 2.093, at the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis.

Thus, there is not enough evidence to support that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of respondents on transactional leadership in terms of formulation of Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO), policy implementation, work management, problem solving and human resources development. These findings imply that what the administrators perceived they have done is congruous to what the faculty perceived.

Level of Organizational Commitment of the Teacher Education Administrators as Perceived by the Faculty and the Administrator Respondents

Table 14. Respondents' Perceptions on Organizational Commitment of the Teacher Education Administrators as Regards Affective

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. would be very happy to spend the rest of his/her career with this organization.	4.55	0.60	VHE	4.23	0.79	HE
2. enjoys discussing his/her organization with people outside it.	4.40	1.05	HE	4.03	0.90	HE
3. really feels as if the organization's problems are his/her own.	4.05	0.76	HE	4.05	0.88	HE
4. think that he/she could easily become as attached to another organization as he/she is to this one.	3.30	0.98	ME	3.92	0.90	HE
5. does not feel like 'part of the family' in his/her organization.	2.15	0.93	LE	3.11	1.29	ME
6. does not feel 'emotionally attached' to his/her organization.	2.15	0.93	LE	3.18	1.26	ME
7. feels that the organization has a great deal of personal meaning to him/her.	4.15	0.93	HE	4.10	0.89	HE
8. does not feel a strong sense of belonging to his organization.	2.00	1.08	LE	3.03	1.30	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.34		ME	3.71		HE
Standard deviation	0.36			0.70		

Based on the weighted mean, the administrators would be very happy to spend their career with the organization to a very high extent. This implies that they are very much satisfied with the organization. However, the faculty felt this satisfaction only to a high extent, not as much as the perception of the administrators, which could probably indicate that they have some expectations.

The overall weighted means on the affective dimensions is 3.34 (moderate extent) and 3.70 (high extent) for the administrators and faculty, respectively. On the account of the prevalence of unfavorable items, the result tends to show a higher level of commitment of administrators than the faculty.

Table 15. Respondents' Perceptions on Organizational Commitment of the Teacher Education Administrators as Regards Continuance

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. not afraid of what might happen if he/she quits his/her job without having another one lined up.	3.55	1.47	HE	3.51	1.17	HE
2. finds it very hard to leave his/her organization right now, even if he/she wanted to.	3.80	1.11	HE	3.97	0.94	HE
3. would have too much of his/her life disrupted if he/she decides to leave the organization now.	3.45	1.10	ME	3.86	0.94	HE
4. would not find it costly if he/she leaves the organization now.	3.65	1.09	HE	3.37	1.10	ME
5. finds staying with the organization as a matter of necessity and desire.	3.84	0.90	HE	4.03	0.86	HE
6. feels that he/she has too few options to consider leaving this organization.	3.70	1.22	HE	3.82	0.92	HE
7. has few serious consequences of leaving this organization.	3.80	0.89	HE	3.50	1.09	HE
8. finds leaving the work would require considerable personal sacrifice — another organization may not match the overall benefits he/she has in this organization.	3.50	1.24	HE	3.93	0.89	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.66		HE	3.75		HE
Standard deviation	0.67			0.70		

Out of the eight items on the perceptions on organizations commitment on the dimension of continuance, six items revealed the same level of perceptions at high extent of the two groups of respondents. These items pertain to not being afraid to quit their job even without another alternative jobs, although they may find it hard to leave the organization right now, even if they wanted to, probably on account of some responsibilities or some unfinished tasks. In fact, staying in the organization is a matter of necessity, considering the consequence of leaving, few alternative options, and the benefit they get from the organization. These perceptions tend to show that financial stability and security is likely a stronger motivation to stay rather than a strong sense of commitment to the organization.

The faculty felt that to a high extent leaving the organization could bring about much description in their existence, probably because of not finding a new job soon. To the administrators, this fact is perceived only to a moderate extent, likely because they may find it easier to look for another job an account of their position and experience.

In the overall, their commitment to the organization in terms of continuance is perceived to be to a high extent on account of some personal considerations, primarily financial and security.

The levels of perceptions of the administrators and faculty are the same in seven (7) out of eight (8) items. Their perceptions differed on believing that moving from one institution to another is unethical. The faculty perceived this to a high extent, while it is thought to

a moderate extent by the administrators. It is very likely that the teachers felt it is unethical for them to leave their students instantly because of their responsibility. This is not so with administrators who are not directly involved with students.

Table 16. Respondents' Perceptions on Organizational Commitment of the Teacher Education Administrators as Regards Normative

Factors/Indicators	Administrators			Faculty		
	WM	sd	VI	WM	sd	VI
1. thinks that people these days move from company to company too often.	3.40	1.10	ME	3.35	1.19	ME
2. does not believe that a person must always be loyal to his or her organization.	2.65	1.23	ME	3.20	1.26	ME
3. believes that jumping from one educational institution to another is unethical.	2.80	1.24	ME	3.67	1.07	HE
4. believes that loyalty is important and therefore feels a sense of moral obligation to remain.	4.30	1.08	HE	4.10	0.90	HE
5. thinks that if he/she gets another offer for a better job elsewhere he/she would not feel it was right to leave the organization.	3.75	1.12	HE	3.91	0.95	HE
6. was taught to believe the value of remaining loyal to one organization.	4.20	0.95	HE	4.04	0.88	HE
7. thinks that things were better in the days when people stayed with one organization for their careers.	4.21	0.79	HE	4.00	0.87	HE
8. thinks that wanting to be a 'company man' or 'company woman' is no longer sensible.	3.05	1.23	ME	3.35	1.14	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.54		HE	3.70		HE
Standard deviation		0.42			0.66	

To a moderate extent, both groups of respondents observed that many people move from one organizations to another too often, not believing that a person must always be loyal to the organization, and that wanting to be a company man or woman is no longer sensible. These perceptions tend to indicate personal welfare should take the priority over loyalty to an organization. There could have been many instances when they should assess situations for purposes of practicality.

This is supported by the overall mean of 3.54 and 3.70, for the administrators and faculty, respectively, verbally interpreted as high extent in the normative dimension of organizational commitment.

Significant Difference in the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Commitment of the Teacher Education Administrators

Table 17. Summary of Test of Difference between the Perceptions of Respondents on the Commitment of the Teacher Education Administrators Using t Test

Dimensions	Computed t Value	Critical t Values	Decision	Interpretation
A. Affective	3.53	±2.093	Reject the Ho	Significant
B. Continuance	0.55	±2.093	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
C. Normative	1.44	±2.093	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant

The table displayed that the computed t value for affective is higher than the critical t value of 2.093 while the computed t values for continuance and normative are between the critical t values of -2.093 and 2.093. It means that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the level of commitment of the teacher education administrators with regard to affective, however in terms of continuance and normative, the respondents' perceptions do not differ significantly.

These findings imply that both groups of respondents have the same level of perceptions in so far as the continuance and normative dimensions of organizational commitment is concerned. It is in the affective dimension that the administrators manifest a better perception than the faculty.

Significant Relationships between the Teacher Education Administrators' Emotional Quotient, Leadership Style and Organizational Commitment

Table 18. Test of Relationship between the Teacher Education Administrators' Emotional Quotient and Transformational Leadership Style Using Pearson r

Variables	Pearson r	Computed t Value	Critical t Values (α=5%,df=18)	Decision	Interpretation
Trustful	-0.25	-1.10	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Transformational	(definite but small)				
Dyscontrolled	0.29	1.28	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Transformational	(definite but small)				
Timid	-0.16	-0.68	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Transformational	(negligible)				
Depressed	0.21	0.89	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Transformational	(definite but small)				

Distrustful Transformational	0.01 (negligible)	0.03	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Controlled Transformational	0.02 (negligible)	0.07	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Aggressive Transformational	0.08 (negligible)	0.36	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Gregarious Transformational	0.01 (negligible)	0.03	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Bias Transformational	-0.15 (negligible)	-0.64	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant

The table displayed that the computed Pearson r 's between the teacher education administrators' emotional quotient and transformational dimension describe that there is very low level of relationship. Since all the computed r values are less than the critical t value of 0.444 at 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. It means that there is no significant relationship between the teacher education administrators' emotional quotient and the leadership style in terms of transformational leadership style in terms of transformational dimension. The emotional quotient does not determine the transformational leadership style of the administrators. Other conditions in the institution could have a hand on how they manifest their leadership style.

Table 19. *Test of Relationship between the Teacher Education Administrators' Emotional Quotient and Transactional Leadership Style Using Pearson r*

Variables	Pearson r	Computed t Value	Critical t Values (α=5%,df=18)	Decision	Interpretation
Trustful Transactional	-0.10 (negligible)	-0.44	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Dyscontrolled Transactional	-0.21 (definite but small)	-0.90	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Timid Transactional	0.01 (negligible)	0.03	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Depressed Transactional	0.25 (definite but small)	1.08	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Distrustful Transactional	0.10 (negligible)	0.44	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Controlled Transactional	-0.07 (negligible)	-0.29	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Aggressive Transactional	0.05 (negligible)	0.21	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Gregarious Transactional	-0.28 (definite but small)	-1.23	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Bias Transactional	-0.09 (negligible)	-0.43	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant

The computed Pearson r's between the teacher education administrators' emotional quotient and transactional as seen in the table indicate that there are very low level of relationship. As the computed r values do not exceed the critical t value of 0.444, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is not sufficient evidence at 5% level of significance to show that there is a significant relationship between the teacher education administrators' emotional quotient and the leadership style in terms of transactional dimension.

The results imply that regardless of their emotional quotient, the administrators may practice transactional style of leadership. Situations in their respective institution may necessitate the adoption of certain style of leadership.

Table 20. *Test of Relationship between the Teacher Education Administrators' Emotional Quotient and Affective Commitment Using Pearson r*

Variables	Pearson r	Computed t Value	Critical t Values (α=5%,df=18)	Decision	Interpretation
Trustful Affective	-0.14 (negligible)	-0.60	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Dyscontrolled Affective	-0.08 (negligible)	-0.34	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Timid Affective	-0.28 (definite but small)	-1.26	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Depressed Affective	-0.30 (definite but small)	-1.33	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant

Distrustful Affective	0.28 (definite but small)	1.26	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Controlled Affective	-0.04 (negligible)	-0.15	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Aggressive Affective	-0.18 (negligible)	-0.77	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Gregarious Affective	0.13 (negligible)	0.54	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Bias Affective	-0.15 (negligible)	-0.64	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Critical Value: r	(20.05) =	0.444			

The table revealed that the computed Pearson r's between teacher education administrators' emotional quotient and affective show that there are almost negligible relationships which, certainly are not significant. Since the computed r value do not exceed the critical value of 0.444, at 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. It means that there is no significant relationship between the teacher education administrators' emotional quotient and affective dimension of organizational commitment. This means that the administrators' level of commitment to the institution may be manifested regardless of their emotional quotient.

Table 21. Test of Relationship between the Teacher Education Administrators' Emotional Quotient and Continuance Commitment Using Pearson r

Variables	Pearson r	Computed t Value	Critical t Values (α=5%,df=18)	Decision	Interpretation
Trustful Continuance	-0.17 (negligible)	-0.71	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Dyscontrolled Continuance	0.14 (negligible)	0.60	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Timid Continuance	0.06 (negligible)	0.26	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Depressed Continuance	-0.29 (definite but small)	-1.30	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Distrustful Continuance	0.02 (negligible)	0.07	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Controlled Continuance	0.45 (substantial)	2.14	±2.101	Reject the Ho	Significant
Aggressive Continuance	-0.39 (definite but small)	-1.78	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Gregarious Continuance	0.23 (definite but small)	0.98	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Bias Continuance	-0.02 (negligible)	-0.07	±2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant

As shown in the table, the computed Pearson's r of 0.45 between teacher education administrators' emotional quotient in terms of controlled and continuance defines that there is a moderate positive relationship. However, the computed r value of 0.444, at 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is to reject the null hypothesis. It means that the moderate level of relationship is sufficient evidence to warrant statistical significance between the administrators' emotional quotient and the continuance dimension of organizational commitment. This implies that who have self-control are likely to stay with the institution. However, between the remaining emotional quotients and continuance of the teacher education administrators' perceptions do not associate significantly.

It is implied by the results that except for being controlled, no matter what their emotional quotients are, their perceptions on their continuance in the organization remains unaffected. It is a good indication that the administrators from the selected SUC as the respondents for this study manifested a solid loyalty/commitment to their respected school. This manifestation could contribute the organization as well the teaching force and personnel to become more enthused in performing their various task. As the results show, factors other than their emotional quotient are being considered also.

As exposed in Table 22, the computed Pearson r's between the teacher education administrators' emotional quotient and normative dimension indicate that there is low relationship (0.35 and -0.35) and very low level of all the computed r values do not exceed the critical value of 0.444 at 5% level of significance. The statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis relationship.

The results show that there is no significant relationship between the teacher education administrators' emotional quotient and normative dimension of organizational commitment.

This result tends to indicate that whatever the administrators believe about their institution is not necessarily determined by their emotional quotient.

Table 22. *Test of Relationship between the Teacher Education Administrators' Emotional Quotients and Normative Commitment Using Pearson r*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Pearson r</i>	<i>Computed t Value</i>	<i>Critical t Values ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=18$)</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interl.13 pretation</i>
Trustful Normative	-0.03 (negligible)	-0.12	± 2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Dyscontrolled Normative	0.18 (negligible)	0.77	± 2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Timid Normative	-0.04 (negligible)	-0.17	± 2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Depressed Normative	-0.10 (negligible)	-0.42	± 2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Distrustful Normative	0.27 (definite but small)	1.17	± 2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Controlled Normative	0.35 (definite but small)	1.58	± 2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Aggressive Normative	-0.33 (definite but small)	-1.51	± 2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Gregarious Normative	0.10 (negligible)	0.42	± 2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Bias Normative	0.06 (negligible)	0.24	± 2.101	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant

Generally, therefore, being timid or not, trustful or not, gregarious or not and bias or not, are not the determinants of the administrators affective, continuance and normative dimension of their organizational commitment.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

Among the school administrators from the selected State colleges and universities respondents, the level of emotional quotient of teacher education administrators from SUC 2 in terms of trustful marked as high degree and generally timid, gregarious and bias to an above average it implies that the though administrator in this school manifested timidity and being biased, it can be clinched that administrators from this SUC also exhibited sociable individuals. These characteristics can motivate the faculty to do their task with a merry heart.

Both respondents perceived almost the same level on the transformational leadership style for all the dimensions. It is in the indicator C- Work management only had a verbal interpretation of high extent and perceived by the administrators. An indication of trust bestowed by the superior to their subordinates.

The school administrators in the Selected SUCs are practicing the transactional leadership style in all the five dimensions. There is a slight opposition in using the same especially in dimension D- Problem Solving. It was perceived by the school administrators and in Human Resource Development which was perceived by the faculty.

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